

mashqalalari” atamasındađı xalıqaralıq ilimiy-ámeliy konferenciyası Nókis: Berdaq atındađı Qaraqalpaq mámleketlik universiteti, 2023. 390-392 b

7. Karamov A. et al. IN MINING ENTERPRISES RESEARCH ON THE STUDY OF GEOTECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES //International Bulletin of Engineering and Technology. – 2023. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 120-124.

8. Jumamuratov R. E. Kaipbergenov. AT «The methodology of teaching chemistry based on the use of computer programs.» //Science and Education in Karakalpakstan. – 2019. – T. 4. – C. 64-70.

PROBLEMS OF WATER RESPIRATORY SYSTEMS OF NUKUS CITY AND PROSPECTS FOR THEIR DEVELOPMENT

D. Jumamuratov
Nukus Mining Institute
G. Abdiganieva, Z. Turlibaev
Karakalpak state university
(Uzbekistan)

Annotation. This work analyzes the state of wastewater systems in the city of Nukus in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the problems of these systems and their solutions. Examples of the implementation of programs to modernize the sewerage system are given: separate sections of sewerage networks were built and re-routed in the city of Nukus; sewage pumping stations were reconstructed; a new technology was used to repair external drainage networks without opening the earthen covering. The documents reflect the condition, problems of drainage systems and plans for their improvement. Various measures for the reconstruction of existing networks and structures are presented.

Key words: *water disposal systems, reconstruction, pumping station, sewerage, sewage treatment program*

Introduction

One of the priorities of housing policy is to ensure comfortable living conditions and accessibility of utilities for the population. The state of the engineering systems of the city of Nukus is characterized by growing physical and moral wear and tear of equipment; insufficient capacity of pipelines and collectors; significant overload of right- and left-bank treatment facilities; lack of an organized storm drainage system; an increase in the volume of generated solid waste and the presence of unauthorized landfills. lands, life support systems, long-term target program, state program. Engineering systems of the city of Nukus must not only ensure the standard level of performance of all life-supporting functions, but also make it possible to implement promising projects for the development of the urban environment, construction of housing and new social facilities and business infrastructure.

Methods

Policy documents aimed at improving the wastewater system of Nukus. The goal of government programs is to improve the quality of provided housing and communal services, modernize and develop housing and communal services, increase the level of reliability, quality and efficiency of the public utilities complex. The objectives of most programs include the development and modernization of water supply, water disposal and wastewater treatment facilities, increasing the reliability of life support engineering systems, and developing the main directions, principles and targets for the development of the city of Nukus.

In 2022, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted on the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022 - 2026.

Within the framework of the Development Strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, including “Goal 34: Development of the system of engineering, communication and social infrastructure of the regions, as well as the service sector,” the creation of technically and technologically modernized local and individual wastewater treatment facilities is especially important, which will ensure the reuse of treated water and reduce excess costs, including for the treatment of wastewater generated in areas without a sewer system. [1,11].

Condition of the Nukus water drainage system. The Nukus “Vodokanal” is in charge of 150.1 kilometers of water supply. Pipes for gravity mode 82.9 km and pressure mode 67.2 km. (Picture 1).

Picture 1. Nukus sewerage system

Pipes for pressure modes are mainly steel and asbestos-cement. sewerage pumping stations pump waste liquid through pressure pipelines to treatment facilities. Wastewater leaving the city of Nukus enters the Main Pumping Station and through this pumping station through an iron pipe with a length of Ø-1000 mm and 15 km is discharged to the WWTP facility located in the Karauzyak region of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

The situation in the area of industrial and consumer waste management in the territory is characterized by the formation and accumulation of a significant volume of waste. At the same time, the problem of their disposal is acute: there are no landfills for waste disposal or such landfills are in unsatisfactory condition. Only a small part of the accumulated production waste is recycled [6,10].

Results and discussion.

The main problems of water disposal and wastewater treatment systems (reliability, quality, accessibility for consumers, impact on the environment) include the following. The depreciation wear of networks exceeds 50%, which causes a significant accident rate. Accidents in sewerage networks occur mainly for two reasons: blockages in gravity pipelines with a diameter of up to 300 mm; soil and electrochemical corrosion on pressure pipelines from sewage pumping stations. This problem can be solved by annually replacing dilapidated networks. In total, from 65 to 70 damages are repaired in Nukus per year. Planned preventative repairs of networks and equipment have almost completely given way to emergency recovery work. This leads to a decrease in the reliability of engineering infrastructure systems.

There is unauthorized drainage of wastewater from specialized vehicles owned by legal entities and individuals in forest areas and into city sewer wells, which increases the load on sewer networks and treatment facilities and worsens the environmental situation [8,9].

There is no clearly formulated system of state obligations to provide the population with clean water (requirements for the quality of water as a food product, the quality of water supplied using centralized water supply systems, and requirements for wastewater treatment) as one of the important public functions of executive bodies of state power and local authorities self-government of municipalities in the field of ensuring the quality of human life [3,7].

One of the priority activities of the investment program is to increase the capacity of sewerage treatment facilities in the city of Nukus. Currently, WWTP is operating at maximum capacity. The total actual flow of wastewater to the complex of treatment facilities in Nukus is ~60 thousand cubic meters. m/day with a design capacity of the WWTP of 65 thousand cubic meters. m/day. The existing sewage treatment plants in Nukus are outdated; they now receive 65 thousand cubic meters of wastewater per day. There is a high degree of wear and tear on communications, pumping and blowing equipment. The condition of the equipment does not allow cleaning to the levels established by the relevant environmental requirements [4,12].

The development of a modern system for drainage of domestic and industrial wastewater, reconstruction of networks and structures that provide a high degree of protection of the natural environment from pollution, is impossible without the development of new technologies [5, 6].

Conclusion.

Program documents aimed at improving the wastewater system show the state of the wastewater systems in Nukus, present problems, ways to solve them, and outline measures to improve the condition of the systems. In addition, specific examples of the implementation of programs to modernize the wastewater disposal system are given.

The implementation of program activities will reduce the level of wear and tear and increase the level of reliability of engineering infrastructure facilities in the city of Nukus through preventative repairs, reconstruction of networks and drainage system structures. The number of emergency situations associated with the shutdown of engineering systems will decrease; the comfort of living conditions for the population in the city will increase by improving the quality of provided public services; rational use of water resources will become more frequent; The ecological condition of the territory of the city of Nukus will improve.

Used literature

1. Указ Президента Республики Узбекистан, от 28.01.2022 г. № УП-60. О СТРАТЕГИИ РАЗВИТИЯ НОВОГО УЗБЕКИСТАНА НА 2022 — 2026 ГОДЫ.
2. G.K.Abdiganieva, Z.T.Turlibaev. Kanalizaciya ham aqaba suvlardi tazalaw. Nokis.Qaraqalpaqstan.2020.
3. Чупин В.Р., Майзель И.В. Оптимальное управление развитием систем водоотведения // Известия вузов. Инвестиции. Строительство. Недвижимость. 2016. № 2 (17). С. 180–192.
4. СНиП 2. 04. 03-97 «Канализация. Наружные сети и сооружения». Ташкент, 1997.
5. Д.Жумамуратов, И. Абдиразаков. Способы очистки сточных вод VI –Международная научно-практическая конференция молодых ученых и студентов на тему «Образование и наука: взгляд на современность», 5-12 апреля 2021 г., Баишев Университет, г.Актобе, Казахстан, С. 258-265.
6. В Иркутске проведут реконструкцию канализационных очистных сооружений [Электронный ресурс]. URL: <http://www.irk.ru/news/20141111/reconstruction/> (06.12.2016).
7. Д.Жумамуратов, Г. Абдиганиева, С. Шалабаева. Управление развитием в водопроводных сетях с помощью ЭВМ с учетом вероятностного характера процесса водопотребления. Вестник Баишев университета, Казахстан, №2 2019 г., С. 108-112. www.vuzbaishev.kz.
8. D.Jumamuratov, I.Makhmudov, A. Seytov, U. Sadiev, U. Jovliev, J. Shonazarov, O.Muminov. Mathematical Models Of Typical Elements Of Water Management Systems. Journal of Positive School Psychology (JPSP) <https://journalppw.com/index.php/jpsp/index> Vol. 6 (2022).
9. Д.Жумамуратов, З.Кидирниязова. ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ БЕЗОПАСНОСТЬ ВОДНЫХ РЕСУРСОВ БАССЕЙНА АРАЛЬСКОГО МОРЯ. Journal of Advances in INDUSTRIAL Engineering Technology Vol.3(7) 2022 http://sciencealgorithm.uz/?page_id=5458.
10. Воронов Ю.В. Водоотведение и очистка сточных вод. М.: Издательство Ассоциации строительных вузов, 2009. 706 с.
11. У.Т.Зокиров, Э.С.Буриев “Сув таъминоти ва Оқова сувларни оқишиш ва тозалаш асослари” “Билим” нашриёти 2012 йил.
12. D.Jumamuratov, A.Gadaev. URGENT CENTRAL ASIAN WATER CHALLENGE: SUSTAINABLE WATER RESOURCES MANAGEMENT. Science and Education in Karakalpakstan №2 (14) 2020, 70 pag., <https://karsu.uz/kk/journal-2020-2/>

УМЕНЬШЕНИЕ ПОТЕРЬ ПОЛЕЗНОГО КОМПОНЕНТА ПРИ ФЛОТАЦИОННОМ ОБОГАЩЕНИИ

Мамбетов Алишер Камалович

*доцент кафедры «Горное дело и технологии производства»
Нукусский горный институт, Каракалпакстан, город Нукус*

Иброхимов Дилшодбек Норимбат угли

преподаватель-стажер кафедры «Горное дело и технологии производства» Нукусский горный институт,

Каракалпакстан, город Нукус

d_ibrohimov@nkski.uz

Санакулова Сабрина Санжаровна, Толибаев Ерлан Амангелдиевич

студенты Нукусского горного института

Каракалпакстан, город Нукус

Аннотация: Флотационное обогащение это процесс разделения минеральных частиц в зависимости от их гидрофобности. В процессе флотации минеральная руда обрабатывается химическими реагентами и воздухом, создавая пузырьки, которые прилипают к гидрофобным минеральным частицам, поднимая их на поверхность. Это позволяет разделить руду на концентрат и хвосты, что позволяет получить более высокую концентрацию полезных компонентов.

Ключевые слова: реагент, гидрофоб, поверхность, измерение, процесс, флотомашына.

Потери в процессе флотации могут возникать из-за нескольких факторов, таких как неполное разделение полезных минералов от нежелательных, недостаточная эффективность реагентов или неправильная настройка оборудования.

Дополнительные аспекты каждого метода:

1. Оптимизация химических реагентов:

- Коллекторы: это химические вещества, которые присоединяются к поверхности ценных минералов, делая их гидрофобными и способствуя их прилипанию к пузырькам воздуха в процессе флотации.

- Пеногены: Эти вещества помогают создавать стабильную пену, необходимую для переноса гидрофобных минеральных частиц на поверхность.

- Регуляторы pH: Контроль pH раствора важен для оптимальной адсорбции коллекторов на поверхности минералов и депрессантов на поверхности нежелательных минералов.

2. Контроль параметров процесса:

- Скорость подачи реагентов: Регулирование скорости подачи реагентов в флотационную ячейку влияет на интенсивность процесса и эффективность разделения.

- Температура: Оптимальная температура может варьироваться в зависимости от типа обрабатываемой руды и используемых реагентов, но в целом повышение температуры может повысить скорость реакций и эффективность процесса.

- Интенсивность перемешивания: это важный параметр для обеспечения равномерного распределения реагентов и минералов в флотационной смеси.

3. Использование передового оборудования:

- Автоматизированные системы управления: это позволяет операторам мониторить и регулировать параметры процесса в реальном времени, обеспечивая стабильность и эффективность процесса.

- Датчики и мониторинг: Системы мониторинга позволяют операторам быстро реагировать на изменения в процессе и предотвращать возможные проблемы.

- Передовые технологии флотации: например, механические флотационные ячейки с улучшенными дизайнами для увеличения контакта между минералами и пузырьками воздуха.